

Table S1. Participating studies in this analysis

Study	Population	Case	Control	Total
BCAC				
ACP	Thai	423	636	1059
HERPACC	Japanese	694	1376	2070
LAABC	Japanese/Chinese	812	990	1802
MYBRCA	Chinese/Malaysian	770	610	1380
SBCGS	Chinese	848	892	1740
SEBCS	Korean	1162	1129	2291
SGBCC	Chinese/Malaysian	533	502	1035
TBCS	Thai	138	253	391
TWBCS	Chinese	889	236	1125
Shanghai				
SGWAS	Chinese	2867	2285	5152
SGWAS_stage2	Chinese	2769	2753	5522
Total		11 905	11 662	23 567